

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3407092

UDC Classification: 338.434

JEL Classification: I15, R19

THE MAIN ELEMENTS, COMPONENTS AND DERIVATIVES THAT FORM THE ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM AT THE ENTERPRISE

ОСНОВНІ ЕЛЕМЕНТИ, СКЛАДОВІ ТА ПОХІДНІ ЩО ФОРМУЮТЬ СИСТЕМУ АДМІНІСТРУВАННЯ НА ПІДПРИЄМСТВІ

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Received 11.02.2019

Vishka I.S. Основні елементи, складові та похідні що формують систему адміністрування на підприємстві. Науково-методична стаття.

В роботі виокремлено поняття системи адміністрування, що є сукупністю компонентів, які взаємопов'язані між собою і виступають як самостійні одиниці, функціонують із зовнішнім середовищем як одне ціле. До таких компонентів, з яких складається система адміністративного управління на підприємстві зачислено: суб'єкт, об'єкт, предмет, чинники, функції, цілі, завдання, рівні, елементи, методи, ресурси, критерії адміністративних одиниць, параметри й інструменти. Встановлено взаємозв'язки між цими складовими, що підтверджує їхню системність у сформованій структурі. Запропоновано розподіл адміністративних розпоряджень і повноважень. Аналіз існуючих компонентів дозволить розвинути та удосконалити систему адміністрування і у подальшому запустити на практиці розроблені удосконалення та пропозиції.

Ключові слова: система адміністрування, компоненти, сутність компонентів, рівні управління

Vishka I.S. The main elements, components and derivatives that form the administration system at the enterprise. Scientific and methodical article.

The work outlines the concept of a system of administration, which is a set of components that are interrelated and act as independent units, operate with the external environment as a whole. To such components from which the system of administrative management in the enterprise is enrolled: subject, object, object, factors, functions, goals, tasks, levels, elements, methods, resources, criteria of administrative units, parameters and tools. The interconnections between these components are established, which confirms their systemicity in the formed structure. The distribution of administrative orders and powers is proposed. The analysis of existing components will allow the development and improvement of the administration system and, in the future, put into practice the improvements and suggestions developed.

Keywords: administration system, components, essence of components, management levels

Companies that seek to profit are forced to clearly build, to establish the structure and interaction of all processes in the enterprise (production, technical, financial, personnel, etc.). This is a pledge, if not successful, at least a comfortable and flexible response to changes, problems and other, both external and internal factors. It is worth noting that domestic enterprises are becoming more and more faced with the issue of flexibility, for which this becomes a key issue and task on the way to development, and the formation of a clear system that would manage this process – the main task.

The current system of administration at machine-building enterprises differs from the same system in the organizations engaged in the sphere of services. This is quite natural, given the end product that is produced on each of them. The scope of most services came to us from the West with already established principles, methods and a well-worked out management system. Regarding industrial enterprises, the established pro-Soviet standards have lost their relevance, therefore, the lack of clear administrative influence undermines all attempts of the enterprise to reach the level of prosperity. Today, it is necessary to clearly identify the goals and objectives of an organization or enterprise, to identify the share of the administrative component in the financial, technical, commercial, accounting and insurance processes [1; 2]. In order to form a system of administration at the enterprise it is necessary to find out and clearly describe which components of this system; what is needed for its existence and continuous functioning, which will prove its presence. Thus, disclosure of the essence of the components of the administration system helps to form a system of mechanisms that will regulate its activities to achieve economic and social effects.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Increased interest in the administration problem is not accidental. Now raise issues of managerial activity, which have practical character, those aspects that were still theoretical studies are materializing and are increasingly used in practice. An example of this

can be the large number of consulting and audit firms that help to establish and establish a coherent management mechanism at the enterprises that need it.

The following domestic scholars engaged in the issues of administrative management in recent years: A.V. Kim [3] (2010), O.V. Rusetskaya [4] (2010), O.O. Romashova [5-7] (2011), L. Ye. Dovgan², I.P. Malyk [8] (2013), O.N. Kostenko, Fomichev [9; 10] (2005), O.S. Sharipova [11] (2011a; 2011b) etc., studied the directions of changes in administrative management, administration tools, resources of administrators, characterizing management taking into account the factors influencing it. The researchers raised the problems of the functioning of administrative management as a system, offered methods for reducing the risks associated with personnel trying to determine the criteria for management efficiency.

As we can see, enterprises are developing, analyzing past experience and applying modern practices, learning the knowledge of competitors, borrowing world practice. Consequently, administrative management occupies an important place in the development of the enterprise, since it takes decisive decisions for it.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Researchers of the administration system [5; 7] are increasingly focusing on the formation of the system and its improvement on the basis of management methods, considering the individual elements that are key to the formation of such a system, trying to evaluate the effectiveness of solutions by working out selected Indexes [8]. It is these studies that help us to clearly identify the components that are mandatory in the system of administrative management.

The aim of the article is allocation of all the characteristics (elements, constituents, factors) that form the system of administrative management and the establishment of interconnections between them, which will confirm their systemicity in the formed structure.

The main part

Since the purpose of our research is to present what constitutes the system of administrative management at an enterprise of any specialization, then the administrative management and system should be defined first.

Administrative management regulates relations within the organization (between levels of management, divisions, collective) and externally (between shareholders, consumers, suppliers), providing effective activity of the enterprise, regulation and conclusion of external relations. This is a system in which the use of quantitative criteria and indicators in the process of making managerial decisions prevails. Controlled in administration is a human factor, but influences it using various methods [12].

According to A. Fayol administration involves the functions of prediction, organization, control,

coordination and disposition, which became established practices and the foundation of the structural-functional approach. Also, administrative management is alongside strategic and operational in the overall enterprise management system.

So, the question arises: what belongs to the system of administrative management? Since the system is a set of components that are interconnected and act as independent entities, they function as an integer with the external environment. The following components, from which the system of administrative management at the enterprise is formed, should include: subject, object, object, factors, functions, goals, tasks, levels, elements, methods, resources, criteria of administrative units, parameters and tools. Now let's look at each of them in detail.

Each system, like every administrative process, can not do without the subject and object. The subject is high level managers, local administrators (lower level administrators), system administrators (those responsible for software, information support, computer equipment). The object of the administration system (the targeted activity) is achievable goals for someone or something that must be achieved within a defined time frame. These may be targets for certain employees, their work, in relation to individual processes at the enterprise and the enterprise itself, and, of course, the employees who are targeted above, as well as stakeholders, the rupture of interests between them, the enterprise as a whole.

The concept of "stakeholders" in the scientific literature has several meanings. Comes from english stákeholder, which means the interested party in the ongoing process. This person or group of persons, or even organizations involved in a particular activity, has a share, rights, claims or interest in a particular system in which they are located and interact to meet their own needs in the process in progress. Such entities become part of the system's source of requirements for the same system [13; 14].

Subject in the administrative department are regularities that affect the object. Very often in the administration of the subject of management has a subjective character, because it depends on the degree of development of the object. An example can be risk management in the administration system, quantitative and qualitative indicators that characterize a person, interaction between objects of management, as well as organizational, legal, technological, psychological aspects and their solution, components and indicators of "breaking the interests of stakeholders".

The factor of the driving force of the administrative system is the human resource, without which it is impossible to imagine the existence of a managerial process, as well as external and internal events, the information factor, the external environment (competitors, market relations, suppliers, political, social, economic, religious, cultural decisions, development NTP, consumer interests, international economic environment), and the internal

environment (technology development, staffing, goals, previous decisions).

The main functions of the administrative process include: forecasting, planning, organizing, managing and controlling.

Each of the individual functions or processes in the enterprise is for the purpose of profit and development of the enterprise. Administration works for the same purpose by adopting effective decisions, increasing the value of the enterprise due to staffing capacity, employee risk management, correct assessment of primary and secondary information in construction and decision making, which will further affect the subsequent processes and development the enterprise itself.

The main task of the administration system is to coordinate the actions of the subordinates, as well as to solve the issues: "what to do?", "How?" And "when?" And to organize and collect reports to check the performed work. All this is happening in the current period of time, the issues are dealt with quickly and organized, regardless of the level of administrative management.

There are three levels of administration in the administration system: the highest, the middle, the lowest. The highest administrators are appointed, which is the director or board of directors, executive and general manager (top managers). The middle level is the functional managers and the lowest one is the managers who are responsible for a particular type of operating activity [12].

Note that not all managers of the entity's management structure are part of the administration. Top and partly middle managers are part of the administrative staff and at the same time as managers (since administrators can be managers, on the contrary – not, or not always). Also, the administrative staff includes all specialists and executives who provide top-level executives. There are no administrators of a number of linear and

functional middle managers and almost all managers of the lowest level production and management departments [11].

The elements of the system under study are administrators of different levels (administrative apparatus), employees of the enterprise, a chain of decisions, a management environment, powers that describe the rights and responsibilities of managers of any level, as well as sanctions for non-compliance. Schematically, the transfer of authority and instructions is shown in fig. 1.

Effective management is accompanied by skillfully selected tools.

Among them are the following: bureaucratic, organizational, legal, technical, resource management tools, monitoring [5-6]. Also distinguish adaptive tools, strategic planning, customer service, knowledge management, corporate culture, 6-sigma. Today we can allocate 1c-Bitrix: corporate portal 1.2.0, which is an internal information resource management system for collective work on the tasks set up, as well as effective internal communication [15]. Tools to manage the staff first of all motivation; construction of the goal and its step-by-step achievement, based on the experience passed (made mistakes); evaluation of employees' performance; application of psychological methods of influence on personnel; subordination of transfer of authority, etc. The general director of one of the leading offices of the consulting company Accenture said: "It is much more important to know how to implement it than" to "implement" [14; 15].

Considering the methods of administration, we can talk about their relationship with tools. Because the method is a way, and the tool is a means. In general, organizational, administrative and disciplinary methods are distinguished [10]. The group of organizational methods includes clearly defined rules and regulations, the organization of work.

Fig. 1. Distribution of administrative orders and powers
Source: compiled by the author on the materials [5-8]

Such methods are standardization of tasks; setting and management of goals; making effective decisions; methods of determining the criteria for assessing the activities of the enterprise, the structural unit, relations between employees, taking into account the hierarchy of authority, as well as the very technology of management responsibilities; methods for assessing the activities of employees; Personnel Management: Coordination and Interconnection. A group of regulatory methods apply when it is necessary to solve local problems, issues on the agenda, issues related to the change or improvement of the course of the enterprise. In such cases, orders, orders, orders, decrees are issued, in which they indicate the essence of the decision and the reasons that influenced its adoption. Such documents contain guidelines and requirements for execution. Disciplinary measures include penalties for non-fulfillment of duties, and the

amount of rewards for merit. Punishment – penalty in the form of fines, lowering the position, dismissal. Methods of rewards Promotion in the form of bonuses, career development, creation of comfortable working conditions.

Management resource is primarily a highly skilled administration personnel, since it is the human resource that processes, uses, and manages all other resources. Resource is something that can be used in its activities, and in administration, it is information, technology, Internet resources, management standards, technical, material, financial security, regulatory acts, regulations, powers and, most importantly, a person working with its potential and skills. Summarizing the above, we propose to bring the components of the administration system into a table (tab. 1).

Table 1. Elements of the administration system and their contents

Elements	The essence of the elements
Mission	Ensuring additional economic advantage for the enterprise by means of forming organizational and administrative methods at the appropriate level of management
The purpose	Organization and coordination of all technical and technological processes at the enterprise: production, personnel management, technical and technological base, supply of raw materials and materials, increase of the enterprise value at the expense of personnel potential for profit
Task	Responds to the question: "what to do?", "How?", "When?", "For someone / something?".
Subject	Individually responsible persons (managers) at all levels of the organizational structure of the enterprise
Object	The employee and the quality of his work, "stakeholders" and their relationship, conflict and the discontinuity of interests, set the objectives of the enterprise, the proper state of technical and technological documentation, orders and orders
Item	Countering risks in the administration system; registration of aspects of planning, organization, motivation, control and regulation in a documentary form; indicators of the gap, quantitative and qualitative indicators, interaction between objects of management, organizational and legal, technological, psychological aspects and their decision, coordination of the process of personnel management
Factors	Human resource, information resources, external and internal environment, related events, political factors
Criteria	Quantitative and qualitative indicators that characterize: the ratio of managers and employees, the ratio of the number of orders, decisions and orders, their implementation to obtain the expected result
Parameters quantitative	The number of administrators, their age, division by gender, work experience in general and in a narrow specialization, the number of orders entered into a separate problem issue
Parameters of high-quality	Business characteristics, personal qualities, empowerment, professional skills, due to it determines how quantitative decisions have a qualitative impact on the management process, clarity and clarity of organizational and administrative forms of management, the result of the implemented decisions
Levels	Higher, Medium, Low (all levels of enterprise management)
Elements / constituents	Managers of different levels of management, employees, stakeholders, chain of decisions, orders, orders, different requirements, fines, reprimands, management environment, as well as the following components of administration: planning, organization, motivation, control and regulation
Tools	Bureaucratic, organizational, legal, technical, resource management tools, adaptive tools, monitoring, strategic planning, customer service, knowledge management, corporate culture, use of 6-sigma control concepts, 1c-Bitrix management system
Methods	Forming documents in organizational, administrative, disciplinary, coordination and mandatory, agreed and recommendatory
Resources	Highly-qualified personnel (managers, employees) their potential and skills, information, available and available technologies, Internet resources, technical, material, financial support, adopted regulations, regulations, powers granted
Structure	Centralized, decentralized, hierarchical (bureaucratic) and adaptive

Source: compiled by the author on the materials [3- 8; 10; 11; 17]

Like every system, the administration system has its own structure. Allocate centralized, decentralized, hierarchical (bureaucratic) and adaptive structures of

governance [16].

Speaking about the administration system, it was believed that the main subject of management in this

process is a person (administrator) (fig. 2).

The criteria by which the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the administrator are evaluated will help us with the improvement of the administration system. The quantitative parameters

include: the number of administrators, their age, gender, work experience in general and narrow specialization. In general, quantitative indicators determine how many decisions are made.

Fig. 2. The system of administration in the enterprise and the main components that form it

Source: own elaboration

Qualitative indicators include: business characteristics, personal qualities, professional skills, due to which determines how quantitative decisions have a qualitative effect on the management process. If the object of research is the enterprise as a whole, then the subject can be considered levels of enterprise development. As V.Yu. Samulyak, R.V. Feshchur, O.G. Melnik, O.E. Kuzmin, "level of enterprise development", is the place of a business entity in a competitive environment; efficiency of the enterprise, taking into account resource, financial and consumer potential [9].

Regarding the essence of administrative and administrative functions and powers in the enterprise administration system, the concept of "authority" should be highlighted, which means the right to perform the assigned duties, functions and tasks when making managerial decisions in order to achieve the tasks. Management functions are part of the organizational system and primarily related to the management of human resources, and administrative functions are aimed at managing the property of the

enterprise through these orders, that is, the conclusion of an agreement between the enterprise and the individual employee, which lists the rights and responsibilities of both parties.

Conclusions

Summing up, we can talk about the specificity of the administration system, which combines the features of management, at the same time is a separate management unit in the enterprise, is included in the system of enterprise management and itself is a system. The listed and examined components of the system under study reveal its essence, and further presentation of the necessary elements of the administration system in the form of indicators of the management process will enable to develop the idea of improving administrative management as one of the important processes in the enterprise, to form a series of criteria that are determinant in the management process. On the basis of the obtained results it will be possible to compile a quantitative description of the administration system.

Abstract

Companies that seek to profit are forced to clearly build, to establish the structure and interaction of all processes in the enterprise (production, technical, financial, personnel, etc.). This is a pledge, if not successful, at least a comfortable and flexible response to changes, problems and other, both external and internal factors. It is worth noting that domestic enterprises are becoming more and more faced with the issue of flexibility, for which this becomes a key issue and task on the way to development, and the formation of a clear system that would manage this process – the main task.

Increased interest in the administration problem is not accidental. Now raise issues of managerial activity, which have practical character, those aspects that were still theoretical studies are materializing and are increasingly used in practice. An example of this can be the large number of consulting and audit firms that help to establish and establish a coherent management mechanism at the enterprises that need it.

Allocation of all the characteristics (elements, constituents, factors) that form the system of administrative management and the establishment of interconnections between them, which will confirm their systemicity in the formed structure.

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Посилання на статтю:

Vishka I. S. The main elements, components and derivatives that form the administration system at the enterprise / I. S. Vishka // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2019. – № 2 (42). – С. 20-27. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No2/20.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3407092.

Reference a Journal Article:

Vishka I. S. The main elements, components and derivatives that form the administration system at the enterprise / I. S. Vishka // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2019. – № 2 (42). – P. 20-27. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No2/20.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3407092.

